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EVALUATION OF THE OPERATION OF A PUMP USED AS A TURBINE (PAT) UNDER REAL OPERATING CONDITIONS IN A DRINKING WATER TREATMENT STATION (DWTS)

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1.- INTRODUCTION

Hydropower currently provides about 20% of the world's electricity consumption and is the main source of renewable energy [1]. Thus, during 2018, global hydropower production amounted to 4200 TWh. [2].

One of the main problems with these plants is the environmental impact they cause during their construction, which is why some experts do not consider plants larger than 1 MW as renewable energy. On the other hand, microgeneration (<100 kW) and pico-generation (<5kW) hydroelectric plants are considered as renewable energy sources because they have a reduced impact on the ecosystem and, at the same time, they can avoid the emission of 2500 Tm of CO₂ per year [1].

The main systems in which there is a possibility of implementing a micro hydroelectric power plant are those in which there is a water flow between two points with a height difference that cannot be used for other purposes. An example is the flow regulation systems in water distribution networks [3][4].

The main difficulty with this type of installation is funding turbines suitable for the required operating point, as manufacturers do not normally work with such low power ranges. Thus, in a microgeneration project, the cost of the electromechanical components will have a higher impact on the total cost of the project compared to other hydroelectric installations. One of the possible solutions is the use of a PAT (Pump Used as Turbine). Unlike turbines, pumps have a wide range of heads and flow rates for different standard sizes, easy installation and short delivery time. [5]. Although the efficiency of PATs is usually lower than that of conventional turbines, the payback period can be significantly reduced due to the lower cost [6][7].

In the project described in this article, microgeneration is implemented in the flow control system of a Drinking Water Treatment Plant (DWTP) to recover part of the energy normally wasted in the control valve. Historical generation data are analyzed in order to characterize the behavior of the PAT, since the performance of this type of turbines is not described by the manufacturers as they operate in a range that is not foreseen in their user manuals.

2.- LOCATION

This article analyzes the behavior under real conditions of an axial flow hydraulic pump used as a turbine (PAT) in a DWTP. The DWTP is located in the municipality of Baiona and is supplied by the Baiña reservoir, which is located at a height of about 50 m above the level of the plant. The plant's flow rate varies between 2000 m³/day and 4500 m³/day, reaching the highest values during the summer due to the influx of visitors to the city it serves. The existing level difference in the level of the water supply makes it necessary to regulate the flow at the plant inlet by means of a valve, for which a gate valve was used prior to the development of the generating installation. The main data of the treatment plant can be seen in the following table *Table 1*.

In order to take advantage of the existing difference in level, a 6 kW microgeneration system was installed using a PAT supported by a butterfly valve for flow regulation. The main reasons for choosing a PAT generation system were the high cost of small turbines for the characteristics at the hydraulic connection of the DWTP and their limited availability on the market.

Heights	DWTP	120 m	Flows	Winter	2000 m ³ /day
	Reservoir	148 m		Summer	4000 m ³ /day
	Water layer	182 m		Peak	6000 m ³ /day
Volume	Reservoir	0.7 Hm ³			
	Reservoir-ETAP pipeline	Diameter	300 mm	PAT-Tank pipeline	Diameter
Type		helic. with welding	Type		metal
Length		approx. 500 m	Length		approx. 4.5 m

Table 1. Characteristics of the DWTP.

3.- ELEMENTS OF THE INSTALLATION

The micro-hydro generation installation consists mainly of (see Fig. 1). Fig. 1):

- PAT turbine. The pump used as a turbine is of the axial centrifugal type with a rated flow of 2300 m³/day and a manometric head of 22.7 m.
- Permanent Magnet Synchronous Generator (see SG in Fig. 1) has a rated power of 10.2 kW and a rated speed of 1500 rpm. The coupling between the PAT turbine and the generator is by means of pulleys with the gear ratio 180:212.
- Inverter or AC/AC converter connected to the grid via a coupling transformer. The generator output is connected to the inverter via a diode bridge.
- Flow control and by-pass butterfly valves.

During normal operation, all water flow passes through the PAT turbine and is regulated by a butterfly valve at the turbine inlet. In high flow situations, a portion of the flow is diverted through the by-pass valve in order to limit the power produced by the PAT. In addition, the system has dump resistors at the outlet of the generator whose purpose is to limit its speed in the event of a power outage, for example.

Fig. 1. Elements of the micro-hydraulic installation

4.- PLANT OPERATING DATA

The facility was commissioned in April 2019 and it was still in operation at the beginning of 2023. The operational data of the facility are monitored by a SCADA developed by Teswater [8], and some of the most relevant monitoring variables are:

- Power delivered by the inverter (P_{inv})

- Flow rate (Q)
- Turbine inlet pressure (P_{t1})
- Pressure at system inlet (P_{in})
- PAT inlet throttle valve position (V_1)
- Position of the by-pass valve (V_2)
- Generator speed (n)

It should be noted that in the operational analysis of this article, situations in which the by-pass valve was in operation, which normally comes into service above 3 000 m³/day, have been discarded. Therefore, the flow rates analyzed are between 1 500 m³/day and the maximum value mentioned above (see Fig. 2). The power supplied by the inverter under the above conditions can be seen in Fig. 2, where it can be seen that approximately 95% of the time the power is maintained between 1 kW and 4 kW with an average value of 2.4 kW.

The turbine inlet pressure is maintained between 2 and 3.4 bar and depends mainly on the position of the turbine inlet valve. The inlet pressure to the system is maintained between 5.6 and 6.6 bar, being most of the time above 6 bar and its value depends mainly on the height of the reservoir from which the DWTP is fed and the head losses in the inlet pipe.

Fig. 2. Histograms of the PAT flow rate and of the power delivered by the inverter.

5.- SYSTEM PERFORMANCE

In order to estimate the performance of the microgeneration system, it is necessary to consider the performance of the whole system, on the one hand the generator and the inverter, and on the other hand the PAT turbine itself. The methodology and performance results for each of these elements are presented in the following sections.

5.1. MODEL OF THE INVERTER-GENERATOR SET

The losses of a permanent magnet synchronous generator can be represented by the expression [9]:

$$P_{gen,loss} = k_n n_{RPM} + k_I I^2 \quad (1)$$

Where $P_{gen,loss}$ is the power loss in W, n_{RPM} is the generator speed in rpm, I is the generator current in A, and k_n and k_I are the loss-related constants. The values of the constants k_n and k_I have been obtained by linear regression from the data supplied by the manufacturer (see Fig. 3), with a correlation coefficient R^2 higher than 0.97. For the inverter, only the constant losses obtained from the manufacturer's manual are considered. The losses of the other elements, such as the coupling transformer or the pulley transmission between the generator and the PAT, have not been taken into account.

Once the losses have been estimated, the mechanical power (P) at the turbine shaft can be calculated as follows:

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$$P = P_{inv} + P_{perd} \quad (2)$$

Where P_{inv} is the power measured at the output of the inverter.

Fig. 3. Coefficients and power losses in the synchronous generator.

5.2. PERFORMANCE ESTIMATION

The hydraulic power can be calculated from the turbine inlet pressure, the outlet pressure given by the height of the tank and the head losses in the outlet section. Since the latter is a very short section, its losses will not be taken into account. Thus, the hydraulic power can be obtained as follows:

$$P_h = Q \times (P_{r_t} - P_{r_{out}}) \quad (3)$$

Where Q is the flow rate in m^3/s and P_{r_t} is the pressure at the turbine inlet in bar and $P_{r_{out}}$ is the estimated pressure in the outlet line.

The result can be seen in Fig. 4 which plots the flow rate of the PAT against the manometric head between the turbine inlet and outlet. The evolution of the power output of the inverter and the estimated hydraulic power with respect to the flow rate is also shown. Finally, the efficiency of both the entire microgeneration system and the PAT is calculated. The maximum efficiency of the PAT is be around 80% while that of the whole system drops to 60%.

Fig. 4. Flow vs head, flow vs power, flow vs velocity and flow vs efficiency curves.

6.- ESTIMATION OF THE BEHAVIOUR OF PAT

When sizing a PAT system, it is necessary to estimate the performance as a turbine, since the pump manufacturer only provides data when operating as a pump. There are several methods in the literature for estimating the performance of PAT systems, Table 2 shows

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the results of some of these estimations for the best efficiency point (BEP) [6][10][11][12]. Based on the values shown in this table and the high PAT performance values shown in *Fig. 4* it can be concluded that the PAT is operating in the correct operating range, otherwise the performance would be much lower [10]. However, these methods only predict PAT operating conditions (speed, pressure and flow) at the BEP. The system under study, like most micro-generation systems, operates at variable speed, so it is necessary to estimate the operation under these conditions, which is not obvious because the pump affinity laws do not apply to PAT operation [13][12],[14]-[16]. One of the most successful ways to characterize the behavior of the PAT is through relationships between dimensionless coefficients obtained through regression techniques [12], [14]-[16], being the most common:

- Specific capacity: $\phi = Q/nD^3$ (4)

- Height coefficient: $\psi = gH/n^2D^2$ (5)

- Power coefficient: $\Lambda = P/\rho n^3D^2$ (6)

- Specific speed: $N_s = \sqrt{\phi}/\sqrt[4]{\psi^3}$ (7)

- Specific diameter: $D_s = \sqrt[4]{\psi}/\sqrt{\phi}$ (8)

Where D is the turbine outlet diameter in m, n is the rotational speed in rad/s, g is the acceleration of gravity in m/s^2 and ρ is the density of water in kg/m^3 .

In this article we take as a reference the relations presented in [16] which predict the behavior of the PATs operating far from the conditions of maximum efficiency (BEP), using for this purpose the dimensionless coefficients normalized with respect to the optimal operating point of the turbine, i.e.: ϕ_t/ϕ_{IBEP} , ψ_t/ψ_{IBEP} and Λ_t/Λ_{IBEP} . The results obtained depend on the method used to estimate the dimensionless coefficients ϕ_{IBEP} , ψ_{IBEP} and Λ_{IBEP} in PAT mode. These values can be considered very similar to those when PAT is operating in pump mode. [17], [18] and can be obtained from the relationships:

$$N_{st,BEP} = 0.9051 \cdot N_{sp,BEP}; D_{st,BEP} = 0.9436 \cdot D_{sp,BEP} \quad (9)$$

Where the subscript t refers to the turbine mode (PAT) and the subscript p to the pump mode. On the other hand, as discussed in the previous paragraphs, these values can also be obtained from the estimates given in Table 2.

The estimated values of the turbine in the BEP have a significant influence on the result of the prediction of the turbine behavior in other operating conditions. In order to evaluate this impact, the performance estimation proposed in [16] is shown below, assuming different values for the BEP in turbine mode. The results of this analysis can be seen in *Fig. 5* where the measured values are compared with those estimated using the fitting functions [16] with different estimates of the BEP in turbine mode (PUMP refers to the method of equation (9) and the rest correspond to the methods and values shown in *Table 2*). The RMSE value of the different methods is used as a factor of merit (see *Fig. 6*), highlighting in this sense the PUMP and Alatorre-Frenk methods for the estimation of the specific height and the Lewinsky-Kesslitz method for the estimation of the specific power. In any case, specifically for the PAT under study, it is possible to obtain least squares fitting functions using a second order polynomial that improves the RMSE results (see FITTED in *Fig. 5* and in *Fig. 6*), although these curves would only be applicable to this particular PAT.

Fig. 5. Specific capacity vs. height coefficient and power coefficient

Fig. 6. Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)

Method	H _t (m)	Q _t (m ³ /day)
Stepanoff	27.5	2536.8
Childs & Hancock	27.5	2793.6
Grover	39.1	2695.8
Lewinsky-Kesslitz	28.4	2964
Sharma	28.6	2688
Schmiedl	37.0	4672.8
Alatorre-Frenk	32.0	3108

Table 2. Estimation of the best efficiency point (BEP) as a turbine from pump data

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7.- CONCLUSIONS

This paper analyzes the performance of a PAT-based hydro microgeneration system based on its operational data in a DWTP for more than two years.

The main objective is the characterization of the PAT, for which it is necessary to model the behavior of the different elements of the system, such as the electric generator and the inverter. This modeling has made it possible to determine both the performance of the PAT and that of the microgeneration system as a whole.

In order to estimate the behavior of the PAT over its entire operating range, a polynomial least squares fit was performed, which gave reasonable RMSE values. However, this method would only be applicable to a PAT with the same characteristics as the one used. Therefore, this result was compared with estimates available in the scientific literature that allow the use of a generic method to predict the behavior of a PAT. For this purpose, it has been used functions including dimensionless coefficients normalized with respect to the Best Efficiency Point (BEP). This type of functions, among the methods consulted, is the one that achieves the greatest accuracy in the results. On the other hand, in order to evaluate the effect of the BEP parameters on the results obtained, different estimates of the BEP were used and the results were compared using the RMSE as a factor of merit. The best results were obtained with the PUMP, Alatorre-Frenk and Lewinsky-Kesslitz BEP estimation methods.

As a general conclusion, it can be said that the use of PAT for hydroelectric generation systems is a viable option, both in economic terms and in terms of predictability of their performance. The latter is achieved through the techniques presented in this article, despite the fact that manufacturers do not provide information on the behavior of pumps operating as PAT.

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ANNEX: SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

ANNEX A: Technical Characteristics of the Installation

Tables A1, A2, A3 and A4 below show the technical characteristics of the different elements of the installation, as well as their operating curves in Figs. A1 and A2. The location of the plant can be seen in Fig. A3.

Type	Axial centrifuge
Speed	2900 rpm
Flow rate	500-2200 l/min
Manometric height.	26.4-16.5 m
Power	10 HP / 7.5 kW
Transmission ratio PAT-Generator	180:212 (≈ 0.85)
BEP (Best Efficient Point)	
Manometric height	22.7 m
Flow rate	2304 m /day ³

Table A1. Pump characteristics

Type	Perm. Magnets Sync.
Power	10.2 kW
Efficiency	91.5%
Voltage	360 V
Speed	1500 rpm
No. of poles/frequency	8 / 100 Hz
EMF	234 V/kmin
Reactance L_d	12 mH
L_q/L_d ratio	100%

Table A2. Generator characteristics

Power	15 kW
Switching freq.	6 kHz
Losses	356W@40°C / 326W@50°C
Voltage	400 V (380-480 \pm 10%)

Table A3. AC/AC converter characteristics

Power	12 kW
Voltage ratio	180V / 400V
Shortcircuit voltage	9.6 %

Table A4. Coupling transformer characteristics

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Fig. A1. Pump operating curves

Fig. A2. Torque and efficiency curves of the generator

Fig. A3. Location of the DWTP and the Baiña reservoir (source Google Earth Pro v. 7.3.4.8642).

Annex B: Plant Operating Data

As an example, figures B1 and B2 show the evolution of some of the monitored variables between the end of April and the beginning of May 2021. The histograms of these values can be seen in figures B3 and B4.

Fig. B1. Position of the valves (V_1 and V_2) and flow rate.

Fig. B2. Turbine pressure (P_t), system inlet pressure (P_{rin}) and generator speed (rpm).

Fig. B3. Histogram of the flow rate at the PAT and power delivered by the inverter.

Fig. B4. Histogram of system inlet pressure and PAT turbine inlet pressure.

ANNEX C: Prediction of PAT behavior from dimensionless parameters

One of the techniques for estimating the behaviour of PATs is to obtain polynomial functions involving dimensionless coefficients. These functions are obtained by means of regression techniques from laboratory measurements of several PATs [15], [16], [18]-[21]. One of the most recent articles in this regard [16] presents expressions obtained from the testing of 32 PATs. These are:

$$\Psi_t/\Psi_{tBEP} = 0.2394 \cdot (\Phi_t/\Phi_{tBEP})^2 + 0.769 \cdot (\Phi_t/\Phi_{tBEP})$$

$$\Lambda_t/\Lambda_{tBEP} = 1.5831 \cdot (\Phi_t/\Phi_{tBEP})^2 - 0.621 \cdot (\Phi_t/\Phi_{tBEP})$$

Where it should be noted that:

$$\Lambda_t/\Lambda_{tBEP} = (\eta_t/\eta_{tBEP})(\Psi_t/\Psi_{tBEP})(\Phi_t/\Phi_{tBEP})$$